

THE MAIN CONCEPT OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS AND LINGUOCULTUROLOGY

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Annotation: This article describes the basic concept in cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology. In modern linguistics, the concept issue is one of the current problems. The unit of concept is closely connected to cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology but there exist specific meaning for each of them.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, concept, linguoculturology, category, linguistics

At the beginning of the XX-XXI centuries, new directions of cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology were formed in modern linguistics. While cognitive linguistics studies language to think, comprehend, and accumulation the knowledge, linguoculturology reveals the relationship between language and culture. In modern linguistics, the analysis of the notion of "concept", as well as the definition of its main features, is one of the current problems. The reason why this concept does not have a single definition is that scholars at different levels of linguistics express different views on its specific nature, essence and structure. The linguistic approach opinions on the nature of the concept is listed in the works of S.A. Askald, D.S. Likhachev, V.F. Kolesov, V.N. Telia. In Particular, D.S. Lixachev S.A. Following Askold emphasizes that there is a concept for each lexical meaning and proposes to consider the concept as an algebraic expression of the meaning. In general, representatives of this direction understand the concept together with the connotative element of the word meaning as its full potential. We can meet the concept concept in different areas and directions and observe that the concept has its own meaning and function in each area. In particular, concept interpretations from the perspective of the fields of psycholinguistics, linguistics, cognitive linguistics, and linguistic and cultural studies were considered. From the point of view of psycholinguistics, the concept is subject to the laws of a person's mental life, and has a dynamic character in the process of cognition and communication. In linguistics, the concept is considered as a linguocognitive and linguocultural phenomenon. The main subject of cognitive linguistics and linguistics is the concept, which reflects the spiritual values of the nation as a unit of thought. In cognitive linguistics, a

concept is a vital image, meaning a language unit. The semantic range of a specific language is formed by the concept. Explanation and understanding of the nature of the concept is through language. The concept itself is a system without analysis, but acts under other concepts. Concept is a collection of knowledge and ideas that manifests the results of life experience belonging to a nation, the attitude of the human mind to life and existence, a term that embodies the thoughts and views of a nation about something. At the same time, the concept is an operational unit of memory, which includes intellectual, linguistic, conceptual systems and the language of consciousness, the existence of knowledge.

The concept represents an abstract unity in the sum of knowledge and experience gained as a result of understanding the world around a person. These views are also presented in Yu.S. Stepanov's conclusions. In his opinion, the concept is part of the culture in the human mind, and in this case, the concept entered the culture as a mental unit of the human world. A concept creates a cultural value in the form of an ordinary human being and permeates the culture and sometimes influences the culture. These views were clarified by N.D. Artyunova. According to the scientist, the concept is the result of interaction of several factors: folklore, national traditions, religion, life experience, image, sense of value. The concept is a unique cultural layer, an image of the connection between man and the universe.

We know that the concept is the result of the thought process that occurs through linguistic units. The concept is unique in that it carries, stores, and conveys information, concepts, and ideas about objective existence, objects, and events reflected in our psyche, and records the attitude of society members to objects and events. The world of concepts is reflected differently in different cultures. Concept possibility is enriched by language speakers as a result of individual emotional and cultural experience. The meaning of the concept is complex. Therefore, scientists consider the concept as a systematic phenomenon. This system is interpreted by the word layer.

In conclusion, it can be said that value is at the center of the concept, it serves the study of language and culture, the principle of value is the basis of culture. Each concept includes a complex mental harmony, the attitude of a person to the object represented, and universal or general, national-cultural, social, language-related, personal-individual components. The lexicon of the language as a means of expressing human culture helps to identify certain cultural conceptual concepts and reveal the essence of the content reflected in the different peoples of the world.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Agzamova Dildora, PhD Linguistic image of the world: the main concept of cognitive
2. Ne'matova N.S: Basic concepts and principles of cognitive linguistics
3. Pimenova M.V: Introduction to conceptual research
4. Safarov Sh: Cognitive linguistic.
5. www.wikipedia.org